

APLIKAČNÉ PROBLÉMY VYUŽÍVANIA MODERNÝCH TECHNOLOGIÍ PRI OBHLIADKE MIESTA ČINU

APPLICATION ISSUES IN THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN CRIME SCENE EXAMINATION

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***Annotation:** The paper deals with practical problems of crime scene examination in the conditions of the Slovak Republic, focusing on crime scene documentation using classical methods and the possibilities of overcoming them through modern technologies – photogrammetry and LiDAR. Based on an analysis of legal regulation, professional literature and the author's own case study, the author identifies systemic deficiencies of classical documentation methods and points to the potential of modern technologies in eliminating them. The paper is based on research carried out within the author's dissertation and formulates specific *de lege ferenda* and *de lege artis* proposals.*

***Keywords:** crime scene examination; photogrammetry; LiDAR; crime scene documentation; practical problems; Agisoft Metashape*

INTRODUCTION

Crime scene examination is one of the fundamental and irreplaceable procedural acts in criminal proceedings. Its purpose is the direct and immediate cognition of the location where a criminal event occurred, and the securing of evidence that may be of decisive importance for the elucidation of the criminal offence and the identification of its perpetrator. From a forensic science perspective, crime scene examination represents one of the basic methods of cognising a forensically relevant event, in which the crime scene is examined as a source of forensically relevant information reflecting the mechanism of criminal activity and the mutual interaction between the perpetrator, the victim, and the environment. (Laca, 2017)

An integral part of crime scene examination is its documentation. It is precisely through documentation that the original state of the crime scene, the position of individual objects and forensic traces, as well as their mutual spatial relationships, can be preserved in a manner that remains usable in subsequent stages of criminal proceedings. Forensic theory has long emphasised that documentation must be carried out accurately, systematically, and comprehensively, as inadequate or incorrect documentation may lead to the irreversible loss of forensically relevant information. (Laca, 2024) (Meteňko, et al., 2025) In the practice of law enforcement authorities, three basic forms of documentation have traditionally been employed – written, photographic, and graphic – which complement one another and enable the capture of various aspects of the situation at the crime scene. (Meteňko, et al., 2025) (Šimovček, et al., 1997)

With the advancement of digital technologies, new possibilities for crime scene documentation are emerging that significantly surpass the capabilities of traditional methods in their potential. Among such technologies, photogrammetry is of primary importance, enabling the creation of three-dimensional models of documented objects or the entire crime scene from a set of photographic images and LiDAR technology (Light Detection and Ranging), which utilises the principle of laser distance measurement to generate a precise point cloud and a subsequent three-dimensional model of the documented space. (Cikhart, 2025a) Both technologies are gradually being introduced in forensic practice abroad, and the professional literature confirms their contribution in terms of the accuracy, completeness, and analytical usability of crime scene documentation. (Galanakis, et al., 2021)

Despite the evident potential of modern technologies, their systematic use within the Slovak Police Force remains limited. Domestic professional literature focuses primarily on traditional documentation methods, while the issue of modern technologies is addressed only marginally and without deeper empirical verification of their practical application. (Cikhart, 2025b) In practice, several application problems can be identified that hinder the broader adoption of these technologies – ranging from insufficient technical equipment of field response units, through the absence of a unified methodological framework, to the inadequate professional preparedness of police officers.

The aim of this paper is to identify and analyse the application problems associated with the use of modern technologies in crime scene examination within the conditions of the Slovak Republic, and, on the basis of an analysis of professional literature and original research, to formulate recommendations directed towards their more effective deployment in forensic practice.

1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Crime scene examination is a procedural act governed by Section 157 et seq. of the Code of Criminal Procedure (Act No. 301/2005 Coll.), the purpose of which is the direct and immediate cognition of the location where a criminal event occurred, and the securing of evidence necessary for the further course of the investigation. (Trestný poriadok) (Strémy, et al., 2024) From the perspective of its procedural standing, crime scene examination constitutes a means of evidence through which law enforcement authorities establish the factual state of the matter by directly observing the crime scene and the objects found therein. (Čentéš, et al., 2022)

From a forensic science perspective, crime scene examination represents one of the basic methods of cognising a forensically relevant event. The crime scene is a source of forensically relevant information reflecting the mechanism of criminal activity and the mutual interaction between the perpetrator, the victim, and the environment. It is precisely for this reason that a properly conducted crime scene examination enables the reconstruction of the course of the criminal event and the identification of circumstances significant for its elucidation. (Laca, 2017) In practice, crime scene examination is carried out by a field response unit, which is a team of police officers designated to perform urgent and non-repeatable acts of a procedural and forensic-technical nature directly at the crime scene. The field response unit is led by an investigator, while responsibility for forensic-technical activities at the crime scene – in particular the detection, fixation, securing and packaging of traces, photographic documentation, video recording, and the preparation of a crime scene plan – rests with the forensic technician. (Laca, 2017) (Laca, et al., 2025)

An integral part of crime scene examination is documentation, the purpose of which is to capture the original state of the crime scene, the position of individual objects and forensic traces, and their mutual spatial relationships. (Laca, 2024) (Meteňko, et al., 2025) In forensic practice, three basic forms of documentation have traditionally been employed:

- **Written documentation** – carried out primarily through a crime scene examination report, which contains a description of the crime scene, individual objects, forensic traces, and other relevant facts established during the examination;

- **Photographic documentation** – enables the visual capture of the state of the crime scene at a specific point in time, recording the overall appearance of the crime scene, the position of individual objects, and the detailed depiction of forensic traces;
- **Graphic documentation** – serves to illustrate the spatial layout of the crime scene and the mutual positions of individual objects and forensic traces in the form of sketches or crime scene plans. (Laca, 2017) (Meteňko, et al., 2025) (Šimovček, et al., 1997)

Forensic theory has long emphasised that crime scene documentation must be carried out accurately, systematically, and comprehensively. Inadequate or incorrect documentation may lead to the irreversible loss of forensically relevant information, which can fundamentally affect the outcome of criminal proceedings. (Laca, 2024) (Meteňko, et al., 2025) Notwithstanding this, in the applied practice of law enforcement authorities, several shortcomings in the area of crime scene documentation can be identified, relating in particular to inconsistent procedures, an insufficient level of cooperation between the investigator and the forensic technician, as well as to the limitations of traditional documentation methods in capturing accurate spatial relationships between objects at the crime scene. (Cikhart, 2025b)

2 MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN CRIME SCENE DOCUMENTATION

With the advancement of digital technologies, new methods of crime scene documentation are gradually establishing themselves in forensic practice, significantly surpassing the capabilities of traditional procedures in their potential. These technologies enable more accurate and comprehensive capture of the spatial relationships between individual objects and forensic traces, the creation of digital models of the crime scene usable in subsequent stages of criminal proceedings, and allow for repeated analysis of the crime scene situation even after a considerable lapse of time. (Galanakis, et al., 2021) Among the most significant modern technologies applicable in crime scene documentation are photogrammetry and LiDAR technology.

2.1 Photogrammetry

Photogrammetry is a method enabling the creation of accurate two-dimensional or three-dimensional models of documented objects or an entire crime scene from a set of photographic images captured from various angles. The principle of photogrammetry lies in the mathematical processing of overlapping images, from which specialised software – such as Agisoft Metashape – reconstructs a spatial model of the documented object or space in the form of a dense point cloud, from which a textured three-dimensional model, an orthophoto plan, or a digital terrain model can be generated. (Cikhart, 2024)

Photogrammetry represents an exceptionally flexible technology in the context of crime scene documentation. Its application requires only a standard digital camera or even a smartphone equipped with a quality camera, while the imaging process itself requires neither complex preparation nor specialised technical expertise. (Rack, et al., 2022) Imaging can be performed at ground level as well as aurally using an unmanned aerial vehicle – a drone – which makes it possible to document even extensive crime scenes or spaces with restricted access. (Cikhart, 2025a) The resulting three-dimensional model enables accurate measurements of distances, areas, and volumes to be carried out, even retrospectively after the completion of the crime scene examination. It is precisely the ability to determine volume – for example in the documentation of illegal waste dumps or other environmental criminal offences – that

represents one of the most significant contributions of photogrammetry to forensic practice. (Cikhart, 2025a) (Cikhart, 2025b)

2.2 LiDAR Technology

LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) is a technology based on the principle of active remote sensing, in which a sensor emits laser pulses and measures the time of their return after reflection from objects within the scanned space. On the basis of these measurements, the position of each scanned point in space can be determined with high accuracy, enabling the creation of a so-called point cloud – a set of millions to billions of spatial points from which an accurate three-dimensional model of the documented space can subsequently be generated. (Galanakis, et al., 2021)

LiDAR technology is available in several variants depending on the mode of application. Terrestrial LiDAR scanners are stationary devices placed directly at the crime scene, capable of capturing a spatial model with millimetre-level accuracy. Mobile LiDAR systems are installed on vehicles or unmanned aerial vehicles and enable the documentation of extensive outdoor areas. (Galanakis, et al., 2021) In recent years, LiDAR sensors have also appeared in commercial devices – such as tablets and smartphones of the Apple iPad Pro and iPhone Pro lines – which significantly reduces the cost of its use and opens new possibilities for routine forensic practice as well. (Jalč, 2012)

Compared to photogrammetry, LiDAR provides higher spatial accuracy and is less dependent on lighting conditions at the crime scene. On the other hand, the acquisition of a professional LiDAR scanner is considerably more costly than the acquisition of photogrammetric equipment, which represents one of the key factors limiting its broader use in the practice of law enforcement authorities. (Jalč, 2012)

3 APPLICATION PROBLEMS IN CRIME SCENE DOCUMENTATION

3.1 Application Problems of Classical Documentation Methods

Despite the long-standing tradition and entrenchment of classical crime scene documentation methods in the forensic practice of law enforcement authorities, several recurring problems can be identified in their application, the common denominator of which is a limited capacity to capture the state of the crime scene – with all its spatial relationships – comprehensively, accurately, and permanently.

One of the most serious and most frequently occurring shortcomings is the **formal conduct of crime scene examination**. In the practice of law enforcement authorities, it is common for a crime scene examination to be carried out in a purely formal manner, particularly in cases involving a misdemeanour – that is, a less serious criminal matter – with the entire act being completed within a matter of minutes, in the knowledge that the perpetrator is unlikely to be identified. Such an approach is a direct consequence of a persistent trend – a high volume of cases and insufficient personnel capacity, as a result of which the time devoted to an individual examination is minimal. A serious consequence of this approach is the potential irreversible loss of forensically relevant information – particularly in cases where a perpetrator subsequently retracts a confession and forensic investigators lack objectively secured evidence. (Jalč, 2012)

A further identified problem is the **inadequate protection of the crime scene** against contamination. Not every police officer is sufficiently aware that the protection of the crime scene takes precedence over any other activities. Members of the field response unit sometimes move carelessly around the crime scene, unnecessarily creating new traces or destroying existing ones, which can have a fundamental impact on the evidentiary value of the secured traces. Similarly, inexperienced officers performing initial acts at the crime scene without a more experienced colleague available commit errors that are very difficult, or in some cases entirely impossible, to remedy. (Jalč, 2012)

From the perspective of **photographic documentation**, several methodological shortcomings can be identified. Photographic documentation as such preserves a two-dimensional image of the crime scene; however, its fundamental limitation is its inability to accurately capture the spatial relationships between individual objects and forensic traces. Measurements carried out manually using tape measures or wheel measuring devices are time-consuming, dependent on the technician's skill, and prone to error. A crime scene plan drawn by hand into the examination report is distorted by the technician's subjective perception, and its accuracy is limited. In the practice of Slovak forensic technical units, it has been found that photogrammetry is not used – or is used only sporadically – in crime scene documentation, and that all relevant traces and the space of the committed criminal offence are recorded exclusively by manual means. (Adamová, et al., 2022)

A particular problem is **the dependence of documentation quality on the subjective factor** – the expertise, experience, and diligence of the individual forensic technician. If the leader of the field response unit approaches the examination inattentively, subordinates typically replicate their errors. (Jalč, 2012) Practice also highlights a profound gap between the theoretical knowledge of recent police school graduates and the realities of actual crime scene work, where these individuals learn primarily from more experienced colleagues who may themselves be marked by ingrained poor habits. (Adamová, et al., 2022)

In summary, classical methods of crime scene documentation are burdened by a combination of systemic (personnel and financial capacity), methodological (inconsistency of procedures), and individual (subjective factor) problems, with the result that crime scene documentation does not always fulfil the requirement of comprehensiveness, accuracy, and permanence of the record. (Laca, 2024) (Meteňko, et al., 2025)

3.2 Application Problems of Modern Technologies

Although modern technologies – photogrammetry and LiDAR – possess the potential to substantially eliminate the shortcomings of classical documentation methods, their introduction into the practice of law enforcement authorities is accompanied by their own application problems.

A fundamental limiting factor is the **financial and technical complexity involved**. Professional LiDAR scanners represent an investment of tens of thousands of euros, and their procurement, operation, and maintenance are unsustainable for standard police departments in Slovakia. Even in the case of photogrammetry, which is more financially accessible, it is necessary to have a licensed photogrammetric software package (e.g. Agisoft Metashape), high-performance computing equipment, and trained personnel capable of using these tools with professional competence. In the conditions of the Slovak Republic, the use of 3D techniques in

the documentation of criminal offence scenes can be described as inadequate, precisely on account of personnel, time, and financial constraints. (Adamová, et al., 2022)

A further problem is the **time-consuming nature of data processing**. While the imaging of the crime scene itself can be completed relatively quickly, the import of data into the relevant software, its automated processing, the generation of a three-dimensional model, its analysis, and the extraction of forensically relevant information are processes requiring several hours of computing time – and, depending on the extent of the documented area, potentially longer. (Adamová, et al., 2022) This time burden represents a non-negligible obstacle in the environment of overworked law enforcement authorities.

A distinct category of problems comprises **the inherent limitations of photogrammetry**. The resulting quality of the three-dimensional model is heavily dependent on the lighting conditions at the crime scene – intense sunlight causes overexposed images, while dim light and darkness lead to underexposure, which can prolong or complicate the entire documentation process. Furthermore, a degree of subjectivity on the part of the technician enters the processing workflow through the configuration of imaging and software parameters. (Adamová, et al., 2022)

An equally important obstacle is the absence of a **binding methodology and uniform procedures** for the use of modern technologies in the practice of law enforcement authorities. At present, there exists no binding procedural regulation or internal directive governing the conditions, scope, and manner of using photogrammetry or LiDAR technology in crime scene examination, which leads to the unsystematic and occasional use of these tools. (Cikhart, 2025b)

4 ORIGINAL RESEARCH AND PARTIAL FINDINGS

4.1 Research Methodology

The findings presented herein are drawn from research conducted as part of the author's doctoral dissertation, the aim of which is the identification and analysis of application problems in crime scene examination in the practice of law enforcement authorities within the conditions of the Slovak Republic. The research is conceived as a combined – quantitative-qualitative – study and consists of three mutually complementary parts.

The first part comprises **an analysis of crime scene examination reports**. The subject of examination is a set of reports from various types of criminal matters, with regard to formal structure, the completeness of the crime scene description, the method and extent of documentation, and the identification of recurring shortcomings. The second part consists of **a questionnaire survey** conducted among investigators, authorised officers, and forensic technicians of the Slovak Police Force, focused on the subjective perception of application problems in crime scene examination, the degree of respondents' familiarity with modern technologies, and their attitudes towards the possibilities of using photogrammetry and LiDAR technology in practice. The third part of the research is **an experiment**, in the course of which classical photographic documentation by a forensic technician and photogrammetric surveying were carried out in parallel at the same crime scene, with the outputs of both methods being compared in terms of the accuracy, completeness, and informational value of the captured documentation.

4.2 Photogrammetric Surveying of a Crime Scene – Case Study

For the purposes of illustrating the potential of photogrammetry in crime scene documentation, field photogrammetric surveying was carried out at a crime scene related to criminal activity involving environmental damage – specifically the illegal depositing of waste. At the same location, classical photographic documentation was simultaneously performed by a forensic technician at ground level.

Photogrammetric imaging was carried out using an unmanned aerial vehicle, with the captured aerial images subsequently processed in Agisoft Metashape software. The output of the processing was a dense point cloud, from which a textured three-dimensional model of the crime scene and a digital terrain model were generated. On the basis of these outputs, it was possible to determine with a high degree of accuracy the volume of illegally deposited waste – which represents forensically critical information for the legal classification of the act and the determination of the extent of environmental damage, and thus for the fulfilment of the constituent elements of the relevant criminal offence under Section 302 et seq. of the Criminal Code. (Cikhart, 2025a)

A comparison of both documentation methods reveals fundamental differences in the informational value of the resulting outputs. Classical photographic documentation captures a visual image of the crime scene from specific angles; however, it does not permit accurate measurement of spatial relationships, areas, and volumes without additional manual measurement on site. In contrast, the photogrammetric model provides comprehensive, accurately measured, and spatially complete documentation of the crime scene, from which any measurements can be extracted at any time – including retrospectively, without the need to return to the crime scene. (Cikhart, 2024) (Adamová, et al., 2022) This property is particularly valuable in cases where the state of the crime scene changes following the completion of the examination – for example, during the removal of illegal dumps ordered by the competent authorities.

The results of the case study indicate that the use of photogrammetry in crime scene examination in cases of environmental criminal activity has unambiguous potential to enhance the quality and evidentiary value of documentation. They also point to the fact that the implementation of this technology into the routine practice of law enforcement authorities will require systemic solutions – above all, the development of a binding methodology, the provision of technical equipment, and the professional training of forensic technicians and investigators.

The facts described above can be identified and compared in the figures below and in their concise captions.

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Figure 1c

Figure 1d

Figure 1a: General view of the outdoor area of the crime scene – illegal waste dump, panoramic shot from ground level (source: author)

Figure 1b: Orientation examination of the crime scene (source: author)

Figure 1c: Police Force officer (specialised unit) during crime scene examination – ground-level documentation does not allow for accurate determination of the volume of deposited waste (source: author)

Figure 1d: Interior of a building filled with illegally deposited waste (source: author)

Figure 2a

Figure 2b

Figure 2a: Aerial view of the crime scene taken from a drone during photogrammetric imaging – flight altitude 49.2 m, resolution 1.49 cm/pixel. The image documents the outdoor area of the illegal waste dump with a clearly visible volume of deposited waste (source: author)

Figure 2b: Orthophoto map of the crime scene generated by Agisoft Metashape Professional software on the basis of 97 aerial images processed into a dense point cloud comprising 74,390,722 points. Photogrammetric processing enabled accurate determination of the volume of illegally deposited waste: 1,859.1 m³ over a built-up area of 680 m² (source: author)

5 CONCLUSION AND DE LEGE FERENDA PROPOSALS

Crime scene examination represents one of the most significant and simultaneously most vulnerable procedural acts in criminal proceedings. Its outcome is determined by a combination of legal regulation, methodological preparedness, personnel capacity, and the technological level of the available tools. The research conducted in the context of this paper confirms that application problems in crime scene examination are not isolated failures of individual police officers, but a systemic phenomenon requiring a comprehensive and coordinated response at multiple levels. (Cikhart, 2025b)

Classical methods of crime scene documentation – despite their entrenchment in practice – exhibit structural limitations that predestine them for gradual supplementation, or partial replacement, by modern technologies. Photogrammetry and LiDAR technology do not represent merely a technological innovation, but above all a qualitative shift in the capacity of law enforcement authorities to capture, preserve, and further utilise forensically relevant information from the crime scene – including such parameters as the accurate determination of volume, area, or spatial relationships, which classical photographic documentation is unable to provide. (Cikhart, 2024) (Adamová, et al., 2022)

On the basis of the analysis conducted and the case study, the following de lege ferenda and de lege artis proposals can be formulated:

- **The development of a binding methodology** for the use of modern technologies – photogrammetry and LiDAR – in crime scene examination, in the form of an internal regulation or directive, which would govern the conditions, scope, and procedure for their use depending on the type and severity of the criminal matter;
- **The introduction of photogrammetry as a standard documentation method** in the examination of crime scenes related to environmental damage, where the accurate determination of the volume and extent of damage is a key prerequisite for the correct legal classification of the act;
- **Systemic education** in the field of modern crime scene documentation methods must encompass both groups of forensic technicians – technicians assigned to the Forensic Science Department of the Presidium of the Police Force, as well as technicians operating within regional police directorates. Equally indispensable is the training of investigators of the crime scene examination. The possession of modern equipment does not in itself guarantee its effective use in practice – if the leader of the field response unit has no knowledge of the capabilities and limitations of these technologies, their potential remains untapped;
- **Addressing the technological disparity** within the Slovak Police Force: under the Recovery and Resilience Plan, modern equipment – including handheld 3D scanners, laser scanners, and drones – was secured for four regional departments of the Forensic

Science Department of the Presidium of the Police Force, based in Bratislava, Nitra, Banská Bystrica, and Košice, with the total investment exceeding 11 million euros. (Ministerstvo vnútra SR, 2025) However, forensic technicians assigned to regional police directorates do not have access to this equipment, which creates a significant technological and capacity disparity within the Police Force and places increased demands on coordination between both groups of technicians during the conduct of crime scene examination;

- **Initiating a legislative discussion** on the entrenchment of modern crime scene documentation methods as a fully-fledged means of evidence in the Code of Criminal Procedure, in the context of the forthcoming recodification of procedural criminal law.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the implementation of modern technologies into the practice of crime scene examination within the conditions of the Slovak Republic is not a matter of the distant future, but a current and resolvable challenge. Investments under the Recovery and Resilience Plan demonstrate that the state is aware of this potential and is addressing it in a systematic manner. (Ministerstvo vnútra SR, 2025) The technologies are available, their potential is proven – what remains key is binding methodological support, education, and the unification of procedures across the Police Force as a whole. It is precisely these factors that form the subject of the author's ongoing doctoral research.

RÉSUMÉ

The paper addresses the application problems of crime scene examination in the practice of law enforcement authorities in the Slovak Republic, with a focus on documentation and the possibilities of improving its quality through photogrammetry and LiDAR.

The identified problems of classical methods include: the formal conduct of examinations due to insufficient personnel capacity, inadequate protection of the crime scene against contamination, methodological shortcomings in photographic documentation, and the dependence of quality on the subjective factor.

Modern technologies represent a qualitative shift – enabling the creation of 3D models with the capacity to measure volumes and areas, including retrospectively. Their adoption is complicated by financial demands, the time-consuming nature of data processing, and the absence of a binding methodology.

The case study (photogrammetry at an illegal waste dump site) confirmed that photogrammetry enables accurate determination of waste volume – information critical to legal classification that classical documentation cannot provide.

The *de lege ferenda* proposals include: a binding methodology, the introduction of photogrammetry as a standard method for environmental criminal offences, systemic training of both technicians and investigators, addressing the technological disparity between the Forensic Science Department of the Presidium of the Police Force and regional police directorates and a legislative discussion on the entrenchment of modern methods in the Code of Criminal Procedure.

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